

ASSESSMENT OF THE LEVEL OF ADHERENCE TO TREATMENT IN PATIENTS WITH HYPERTENSION ACCORDING TO THE RESULTS OF THE "STEPS" STUDY

Narmukhamedova Nazira
Asadov Khusan

Center for the development of professional qualifications of medical workers,
Tashkent city, Republic of Uzbekistan

e-mail: nnarmukhamedova@jpib.uz

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Relevance. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), arterial hypertension (H) is considered a non-infectious pandemic that affects the socio-economic losses of society. The prevalence of hypertension in the world is quite high and amounts to 30-45% among the adult population; increases with age and reaches 62% in persons over 60 years of age [1]. Despite numerous studies on the diagnosis and treatment of arterial hypertension, the availability of various treatment methods and a large selection of drugs and their combinations, it is still not possible to prevent the development of cardiovascular complications (myocardial infarction, stroke), which lead to patient disability and premature mortality [2].

The main problem in the management of patients with hypertension is low public awareness of the disease, irresponsible attitude towards their disease, unwillingness to control blood pressure (BP) levels and low adherence to treatment [3].

Purpose. In order to assess the population's attitude towards their health and determine the adherence of patients with hypertension to treatment, an analysis of the results of the WHO «STEPS» study was carried out among the population 18-64 years old [4].

Methods and techniques. According to the research methodology: at the first stage, a survey of 4,350 residents of the republic was conducted using a standard questionnaire to identify patients with high blood pressure and established arterial hypertension and their attitude to treatment. At the second stage, blood pressure levels were measured, and at stage 3 - a laboratory examination was carried out.

Results. As the study results showed, 46.2% of the population had not previously measured their blood pressure, among them there were 2 times more men than women (35.1% and 16.6%, respectively). In 14.7% of residents, an increase in blood pressure was detected for the first time within the last 12 months. And in 3.8% of patients, arterial hypertension was previously diagnosed. In the last 12 months, the diagnosis of arterial hypertension was established most often in the age group of 45-69 years, in men - 23.4% and women 32.4%, and much less often in the young and middle age groups. Among them, only 73.3% of hypertensive patients who had previously been diagnosed with elevated blood pressure followed doctors' instructions and took medications to lower blood pressure over the past 2 weeks, but 50.4% of them took medicinal herbs or folk remedies to lower blood pressure. This suggests that even despite the treatment prescribed by the doctor, blood pressure levels are not controlled, these patients are at high risk of developing cardiovascular complications. This is due to patients' low adherence to treatment and a frivolous attitude towards their health.

Conclusion. Thus, analysis of the study results showed a low level of patients seeking medical attention and a reluctance to regularly measure blood pressure and take medication. Low

adherence of patients with hypertension to treatment will lead to the development of cardiovascular complications and an increase in premature mortality from them.

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